

Dig into history: Repurposing the lost revolutionary tunnel in Kawit, Cavite

Amis Danielle D. Dulfo*, Ed Christian C. Gamboa, Junichi M. Ishikawa, Jamie Rizelle E. Perez, Trixia Mae Siladio, Marco D. Sison, Titus Carl Delmoro
Tourism Management Department, School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

This research was categorized to repurpose, promote, and analyze the perspective of individuals including the residents of Kawit, living legends, and historian regarding the lost revolutionary tunnel in Kawit, Cavite. This quantitative research uses survey method from 30 respondents of Kawit, Cavite to provide information and understanding about repurposing the lost revolutionary tunnel. Based on the findings of the study, respondents agreed that repurposing of the lost tunnels can have beneficial economic gains to boost the tourism sector of the area, as they perceived that it will not really promote heritage tourism. In addition, even though there was a slight agreement that repurposing will preserve the surrounding environment, it was the government should have a good development plan to put such initiative in place. However, they disagreed to the transformation of the lost tunnels into tourist attractions in terms of historical value and partly agree in terms of tourism development plan and environmental benefits, however, promotion can be done to boost tourist visits to the said lost tunnels, as the disagreement with the preservation of the historical value of the tunnels is more resounding. They still do agree that if the repurposing is pushed through, safety and security of the tourists and the area will have to be given the utmost priority. The respondents proposed marketing strategies to increase tourism in the area in terms of traditional marketing (print media marketing and event marketing and digital marketing (social media marketing and influencer marketing). This proved that the most ideal choice to boost the lost tunnel in Kawit, Cavite is by promotion. Repurposing the lost tunnels must be reconsidered and alternative ways of using them to boost the area's tourism should be studied.

Keywords: Historical site; Lost revolutionary tunnel; Tourism; Repurposiveness; Kawit.

To cite this article:

Dulfo, A. D. D., Gamboa, E. C. C., Ishikawa, J. M., Perez, J. R. E., Siladio, T. M., Sison, M. D., & Delmoro, T. C. (2022). Dig into history: Repurposing the lost revolutionary tunnel in Kawit, Cavite. *SDCA Journal of Tourism Management*, 3, 11-18.

Introduction

Cavite, named from the word Kawit, which simply means hook, owing its name to the hook-shaped mass of land on the old Spanish map. Cavite is known by a history with a large number of National Heroes or is even sometimes dubbed as the "Land of Braves". Katipuneros back in 1896 to 1898 used network tunnels to evade being captured by Spanish forces during the Philippines Revolution. The tunnel is the reason why the "Battle of Imus" in the Cavite was successfully defended in 1896, which was the first major battle of the Philippine Revolution. Emilio Aguinaldo also used the tunnels against the Spaniards, which resulted in a Filipino Victory. Moreover, it was also used to enter Cavite undetected.

During World War II, the Aguinaldo Shrine located in Kawit, Cavite contains a bomb shelter created by Emilio Aguinaldo that was used as a secret passageway through the Church of Kawit. Aguinaldo Shrine is currently a tourist spot attraction in Kawit, Cavite. This is also known commemorated place due to the history this tourist spot holds: objects, secrets tunnels, bomb shelter, and many more (Blitz, 2010).

Most tunnels in Cavite are ancient because of the historical events that took place. Some tunnels were constructed as a passageway during war that served as a defense system for the military, bomb-proof storage, and personal bunker. Nowadays, there are tunnels used as a tourist spot, an underground pathway for vehicles and few are considered as underground diversion dams (Newman, 2020).

The word “tunnel” itself came from France to England; however, Oxford English Dictionary gave its first definition of the word tunnel last 15th century, which means for “catching partridges.” It is a tube-shaped net into which birds can be coaxed, which is usual for the stalker to pose a cow or horse. Marc Isambard Brunel, a French engineer from 1818, created a tool that let workers dig tunnels under rivers without dealing with mud and water, which used to mess up their work. His “tunnel shield” was a rectangular wall made of cast iron with many small shutters. The Thames tunnel designed by Brunel is built under the River Thames in London which is connected to Rotherhithe and Wapping.

On March 25, 1843, the first tunnel was built beneath a river, and it was made available for the public to use. At that time, building a tunnel under a river was not possible because in 1828, water leaked into the tunnel and caused six workers to drown. The construction was paused until two engineers found a smart and creative way to solve the problem. Marc Brunel and Thomas Cochrane got an idea from mollusks that helped change how tunnels were built. It comes from a naval shipworm, which is a type of saltwater clam that has a strong but reduced shell, and the animal has a worm-like body. Animals use calcareous plates to scrape and make holes in the wood to complete the Thames Tunnel (Bressan, 2018).

In Fort McKinley, Philippines, there is a tunnel called the 1910 Fort Bonifacio War Memorial Tunnel. This tunnel was part of Fort William McKinley, a military base built by the US Military Government of the Philippines in 1902. The tunnel was first used to move military supplies and war equipment through. The Fort McKinley Tunnel was meant to set up an underground system to warn about air attacks without being affected by bombings. The Air Warning Service of the Army Air Force is known as “*The Fort McKinley Project*.” It was supposed to be part of making the country’s communication systems more modern. Digging for the tunnel started in October 1941 (Torres, 2020; Weir, 2021).

In Ilagan City, Isabela, Philippines, there is a war tunnel called the Ilagan Japanese Tunnel, which was part of a military base that the Japanese government built as a headquarters for their soldiers during World War II. It can be found in Santo Tomas village, which is located in Ilagan City, in the province of Isabela. It is one of the few tunnels that are still left in the province (Villano, 2018).

The Malinta Tunnel is a network of tunnels built by the United States Army Corps of Engineers on the island of Corregidor in the Philippines. At first, it was used as a safe place to store things and shelter people from bombs, but later it was turned into a hospital that could hold 1,000 patients. Today, Malinta Tunnel is used as a venue for audio-visual presentations by the National Artist, Lamberto V. Avellana, which includes events that happened during World War II, such as the evacuation of President Quezon and General MacArthur by Motor Torpedo Boat Squadron Three from Corregidor to Mindanao (Llora, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

This study identifies the different tunnel that was abandoned, giving it a purpose again. Some people believe that it is used for hiding of the Filipino soldiers. Furthermore, this attempts to answer the following:

1. How do the respondents assess the transformation of the lost tunnels into tourist attraction in terms of;
 - a) Economic Benefits;
 - b) Tourism Development Plans;
 - c) Environmental Impacts;
 - d) Historical and Cultural Impacts;

- e) Safety and Security
2. What are the marketing strategies that may be proposed to increase the tourism in the lost tunnels of Kawit, Cavite?
- a) Traditional Marketing
- b) Digital Marketing

Methodology

This research design is descriptive quantitative research that is conducted with the use of survey method. The researchers used this method of data collection to provide a lot of information and understanding about repurposing the lost revolutionary tunnel. The respondents of this study cover 30 people, including the residents of Kawit area where tunnel is located, living legends in Cavite, and historian.

The data used in this research was collected through survey questionnaires that were approved by two faculty members of the School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management (SIHTM). The survey questionnaire is pursued typically regarding the perspective of the respondent in terms of repurposing the historical site. The survey questionnaire would also determine the possible marketing strategy that may be proposed to increase the number of tourists.

In this study, quota sampling technique was used. Quota sampling method refers to non-probability sampling, and it can be defined as “a sampling method of gathering representative data from a group”. In this method, the respondents were the residents, living legends of Cavite, and historian. The analysis of this study is critically analyzed and objectively interpreted through correlating it to different articles and research. The 4-point Likert scale is used in Table 1.

Table 1. 4-point Likert Scale

Numerical Rating	Numerical Range	Categorical Response
4	3.51-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3	2.51-3.50	Agree (A)
2	1.76-2.50	Disagree (D)
1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents (N = 30)

Age	N	%	Gender	N	%	Occupation	N	%
20 – 30	2	6.67	Male	19	63.33	Zoning	13	43.33
31 – 40	9	30.00	Female	11	36.67	Living Legend*	1	3.33
41 – 50	12	40.00				Historian	2	6.67
51 – 60	6	20.00				Tourism officer	11	36.67
Above 60	1	3.33				Undisclosed	3	10.00

Table 2 below shows the breakdown of the respondents regarding age, gender, and occupation. Sixty percent (60%) of the total respondents are above 40 years old and are natives of Kawit since birth and can therefore be considered very knowledgeable about the area. Thirteen respondents (43.33%) are connected with the City of Zoning Administration Office, by which the main responsibility is to “protect the character and stability of residential, commercial, industrial, institutional establishment and open spaces within the locality.” Another 11 respondents (36.67%) work as tourism officers or personnel in the area. Clearly, 90% of the respondents, including the historians and the living legend, can be considered very knowledgeable about the topic in this study making them very qualified to respond to both parts of the survey questionnaire.

Table 3. Assessment of the Transformation of the Lost Tunnels into Tourist Attraction

Factors	Statements	Verbal Interpretation
Economic Benefits	The repurposing of the tunnel will generate jobs for the locals.	Strongly Agree 3.47
	The government and its people will benefit if the historical tunnels are repurposed	Strongly Agree 3.27
	The repurposing of the tunnel will boost the tourism in Kawit, Cavite	Agree 3.23
	The growth in tourism will help to promote the local products of Kawit, Cavite	Agree 2.83
	Repurposing old tunnels will help government save funds on construction.	Agree 2.73
	Summative Mean	Agree 3.11
Tourism Development Plans	The historical tunnels will have a new purpose, specifically as a tourist destination.	Agree 2.57
	The government should maintain sustainable tourism.	Agree 3.03
	The government have the resources, knowledge and is capable of repurposing the lost tunnels.	Agree 2.67
	A tourism marketing plan should be developed to promote the old tunnels.	Strongly Agree 3.27
	The government should be consistent in funding the sustenance of the old tunnels.	Strongly Agree 3.50
	Summative Mean	Agree 2.99
Environmental Impacts	The repurposing of old tunnels will help to save energy and materials.	Agree 3.00
	The government will take consideration in preserving the environment on the area.	Disagree 2.33
	This will help raise awareness about the benefit of recycling old infrastructures.	Agree 2.93
	The caretakers of the tunnel will be able to maintain cleanliness in the area.	Agree 2.93
	The increase in tourist will not contribute to the pollution in the area.	Strongly Disagree 1.67
	Summative Mean	Agree 2.57
Historical and Cultural Factors	The historical value of the tunnels will still be preserved.	Disagree 1.90
	As a tourist attraction, it should include educating the tourists about the history and value of the tunnels.	
	The repurposing of the tunnel will help tourist understand the culture of the locals.	Agree 3.10
	The repurposing of the tunnel will promote heritage tourism.	Disagree 2.20
	The repurposing of the tunnel will gain an appreciation of the past	Agree 3.00
	Summative Mean	Disagree 1.90
Safety and Security	The government should fortify the structure of the tunnels to ensure the safety of the tourists.	Strongly Agree 3.37
	Tour guides should be hired to lead the tourists.	Agree 3.07
	There should be regular maintenance to test the stability of the tunnels	Strongly Agree 3.57
	The tunnels should be well-lit and have proper ventilation.	Strongly Agree 3.40
		Summative Mean

Table 3 shows the assessment of transformation of lost tunnels. This reveals that the respondents generally strongly agreed in terms of economic benefits, with a summative mean average of 3.42, that the transformation of lost tunnels will be to the area's advantage. Majority of respondents agree that it would lead to job creation (mean: 3.47). These results show a positive view of the project's economic potential, especially when it comes to jobs and tourism (Garau-Vandall et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2012). However, the less enthusiastic attitude towards local products shows that while tourism might help the local economy, it might not benefit all areas in Kawit.

The respondents also agreed, with a summative mean of 2.99, to all the items in the tourism development plan. Survey participants clearly prefer the integration of the tunnels in a sustainable tourism plan. They most strongly support getting government funding to maintain the tunnels over the long term (with an average score of 3.50). The focus on creating a marketing plan and having steady funding shows that people understand the need for long-term planning to make the project work (Brüggen et al., 2017).

In terms of environmental impacts, though the summative mean of 2.57 still falls under "agree", the respondents were not unanimous in their agreement that the transformation of lost tunnels will preserve the surrounding environment. Most people agree that using the tunnels again could help save energy and materials (mean: 3.00). This also suggests that the government needs to take environmental issues more seriously to make sure the project does not harm the local environment (Tan et al., 2020).

In terms of historical and cultural factors, the respondents disagreed, with a summative mean of 2.42, to the transformation of lost tunnels as they thought it will not preserve the historical value of the tunnels nor will it promote heritage tourism. The low average score shows that many people worry the project might damage the cultural value and historical importance of the tunnels. Although some people liked the idea of turning the tunnels into a cultural and historical site, others said that repurposing tunnels will not gain an appreciation of the past. People agreed that the tunnels should teach tourists about their history and cultural importance (mean: 3.10), but they were not as satisfied with the idea that the tunnels' historical value would be kept safe (mean: 1.90). This is especially worrying because it shows there might be a problem between growing tourism and keeping historical sites safe (García-Hernández et al., 2017; Timothy, 2014).

Lastly, respondents agreed, with a summative mean of 3.42, that should the transformation of lost tunnels push through, safety and security measures should be put in place. Most people agree that the government should do a lot to keep tourists safe. There is strong support for making the tunnels fortified (average rating: 3.37), conducting maintenance regularly (average rating: 3.57), and making sure they have good lighting and ventilation (average rating: 3.40). These findings show that the public prioritizes the most about safety when using old buildings for tourism, meaning the project needs to handle safety issues carefully and consistently (Becken & Hughey, 2013; Orîndaru et al., 2021).

Table 4. Traditional and Digital Marketing Approaches

Approach	Particular	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Traditional Marketing	Marketing through Direct Mail	2	6.66%	6
	Print Media Marketing	19	63.33%	2
	Broadcast Marketing	13	43.33%	3
	Out-of-Home Marketing	7	23.33%	5
	Telemarketing	10	33.33%	4
	Event Marketing	22	73.33%	1
Digital Marketing	Social Media Marketing	30	100%	1
	Influencer Marketing	18	60%	2
	Email Marketing	5	16.66%	6
	Content Marketing	12	40%	4
	Search Engine Optimization Marketing	14	46.66%	3
	Affiliate Marketing	3	10%	7
	Pay-Per-Click Marketing	8	26.66%	5

Table 2 determines the possible marketing strategies to increase the tourism in the lost tunnels of Kawit, Cavite. Respondents are given marketing strategies options through the survey questionnaire wherein they can decide which among these marketing strategies could be proposed to increase tourism in the lost tunnels.

Among the traditional marketing strategies, Event Marketing came first with 22 respondents (73.33%), implying that interacting in person, attending events, and doing promotions on the ground are seen as the best traditional ways to market. It is essential to connect directly with possible tourists by holding festivals, shows, and cultural events to help promote places like historical tunnels (Ma & Lew, 2012; Stankova & Vassenska, 2015). It can be noticed that Direct Mail Marketing came in last place with just two respondents (6.66%), indicating the least effective traditional methods in today's context. This might be because people are no longer engaged with it anymore and it has become less relevant. Results suggest that traditional marketing methods that involve interaction and are visually appealing are preferred over those that are static or rely on direct contact.

In terms of digital marketing, Social Media Marketing came first with 100% of the respondents, showing that all respondents prefer this method, seeing it as the best and most powerful way to promote products or services. This outcome shows how social media is commonly used to share information, find travel destinations, and promote tourism, which makes it a key factor for attracting both locals and visitors from elsewhere (Munar & Jacobsen, 2014). The lowest-ranked strategy out of all the marketing methods is Affiliate Marketing, with only 10% of people choosing it. This might be seen as uninteresting or ineffective for promoting tourism.

Results clearly show that people prefer digital marketing over traditional marketing, with social media becoming the biggest influence in all factors. But traditional approaches, like event-based and print marketing, are still important, especially when it comes to promoting cultural and historical tourism in local areas. These results show that using various digital tools, like social media and influencer marketings, along with some traditional methods, such as event and print marketing, would work best for promoting tourism projects such as repurposed historical tunnels (Cowie & Khoo, 2014). Using this combined approach can help reach more people, get them involved, and ensure everyone is aware across various groups.

Conclusion

This research investigated the transformation of the lost tunnels in Kawit, Cavite into tourist attractions in terms of economic benefits, tourism development plan, environmental impacts, historical and cultural factors and safety and security. Based on the findings of the study, respondents agreed that repurposing of the lost tunnels can have beneficial economic gains to boost the tourism sector, as they perceived that it will not really promote heritage tourism. In addition, even though there was a slight agreement that repurposing will preserve the surrounding environment, the government should have a good development plan to put such initiative in place. However, they disagreed to the transformation of the lost tunnels into tourist attractions in terms of historical value and partly agree in terms of tourism development plan and environmental benefits. Promotion can be done to boost tourist visits to the said lost tunnels, as the disagreement with the preservation of the historical value of the tunnels is more resounding. They still do agree that if the repurposing is pushed through, safety and security of the tourists and the area will have to be given the utmost priority. The respondents proposed marketing strategies to increase tourism in the area in terms of traditional marketing which are print media marketing and event marketing, while social media marketing and influencer marketing in terms of digital marketing.

The data proved that the most ideal choice to boost the lost tunnel in Kawit, Cavite is promotion. Local government units or investors should focus on promoting the lost tunnel in Kawit, Cavite through social media and direct marketing to increase tourism. It is recommended for the government to invest more on repurposing old structures into tourist attraction and promoting heritage tourism to provide benefit to the locals. The repurposing of the lost tunnels, however, must be reconsidered and alternative ways of using them to boost the area's tourist should be studied.

It is recommended for future researchers to use the data as basis for future investigation focusing on the advancement of ideas in this chosen field of study which would be carried out by students or faculty members from other colleges or institutions and to determine other possible ways in developing lost tunnels and other old structures into a tourist spot. Future studies can focus on the following areas: boosting heritage tourism, developing ways to preserve historical value of old buildings, creating a tourism development plan, and sustaining the operation of heritage attraction.

References

- Becken, S., & Hughey, K. F. (2013). Linking tourism into emergency management structures to enhance disaster risk reduction. *Tourism Management*, 36, 77-85.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2012.11.006>
- Blitz, A. (2010). The Philippines: The contested state. In S. C. M. Paine (Ed.), *Nation building, state building, and economic development* (pp. 48-65). Routledge.
<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315702186-5/philippines-contested-state-amy-blitz>
- Bressan, D. (2018, March 25). *175 years ago the first modern tunnel was built, inspired by a burrowing animal*. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/davidbressan/2018/03/25/175-years-ago-the-first-modern-tunnel-was-built-inspired-by-a-burrowing-animal/>
- Brüggen, E. C., Hogreve, J., Holmlund, M., Kabadayi, S., & Löfgren, M. (2017). Financial well-being: A conceptualization and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 79, 228-237.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.03.013>
- Cowie, B., & Khoo, E. (2014). Digital tools disrupting tertiary students' notions of disciplinary knowledge: Cases in history and tourism. *Education Sciences*, 4(1), 87-107.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci4010087>
- Garau-Vadell, J. B., Gutierrez-Taño, D., & Diaz-Armas, R. (2018). Economic crisis and residents' perception of the impacts of tourism in mass tourism destinations. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 7, 68-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2016.08.008>
- García-Hernández, M., De la Calle-Vaquero, M., & Yubero, C. (2017). Cultural heritage and urban tourism: Historic city centres under pressure. *Sustainability*, 9(8), 1346.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su9081346>
- Liu, W., Vogt, C. A., Luo, J., He, G., Frank, K. A., & Liu, J. (2012). Drivers and socioeconomic impacts of tourism participation in protected areas. *PloS One*, 7(4), e35420.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0035420>
- Llora, M. (2012). *Transnational Bataan memories: Text, film, monument, and commemoration* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Hawaii at Manoa).
<https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/ed5b2627-59a0-4f6e-a118-3bdd67e47650/content>
- Ma, L., & Lew, A. A. (2012). Historical and geographical context in festival tourism development. *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 7(1), 13-31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743873X.2011.611595>
- Munar, A. M., & Jacobsen, J. K. S. (2014). Motivations for sharing tourism experiences through social media. *Tourism Management*, 43, 46-54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.01.012>

- Newman, C. N. (2020). *Douglas MacArthur's nation-building: The reconstruction of Japan* (Master's thesis, Liberty University). <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/masters/638/>
- Orîndaru, A., Popescu, M. F., Alexoaei, A. P., Căescu, Ș. C., Florescu, M. S., & Orzan, A. O. (2021). Tourism in a post-COVID-19 era: Sustainable strategies for industry's recovery. *Sustainability*, *13*(12), 6781. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126781>
- Stankova, M., & Vassenska, I. (2015). Raising cultural awareness of local traditions through festival tourism. *Tourism & Management Studies*, *11*(1), 120-127. <https://www.tmstudies.net/index.php/ectms/article/view/766>
- Tan, J. S., Elbaz, K., Wang, Z. F., Shen, J. S., & Chen, J. (2020). Lessons learnt from bridge collapse: A view of sustainable management. *Sustainability*, *12*(3), 1205. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12031205>
- Timothy, D. J. (2014). Contemporary cultural heritage and tourism: Development issues and emerging trends. *Public Archaeology*, *13*(1-3), 30-47. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1465518714Z.00000000052>
- Torres, J. (2017, July 12). *Tunnel vision: Fort Bonfacio War Tunnel restoration*. BluPrint. <https://bluprint-onemega.com/architecture/heritage/tunnel-vision-bonfacio-war-tunnel/>
- Villano, A. (2018, February 18). *Travel diaries: Discovering Isabela's rich history*. Rappler. <https://www.rappler.com/life-and-style/travel/195784-isabela-ilagan-sanctuary-japanese-tunnel/>
- Weir, K. L. (2021). *A heritage of freedom: monuments and the American legacy in the Philippine memoryscape, 1898-1978* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nottingham). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/fcb5c7f34eb74da9343b293001372caa/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=51922&diss=y>